

Synthesis and spectroscopic studies on oxovanadium(IV) complexes with hydrazones containing indole ring

Om Prakash Pandey*, Soumitra Kumar Sengupta and Jitendra Kumar Pandey

Department of Chemistry, DDU Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur-273 009, India

E-mail : sengupta2002@yahoo.co.in

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A new series of complexes of type $[VO(L)H_2O]$ (L = hydrazone ligands derived from isatin and aromatic acid hydrazides) has been prepared. Tentative structures of the complexes have been proposed on the basis of elemental analysis, electrical conductance, magnetic moment and spectral (IR, electronic and EPR) data. The X-band EPR spectra of all the complexes were recorded at room temperature and at liquid N_2 temperature. The room temperature EPR spectra do not show anisotropy because of rapid tumbling of molecules in solution. The spectral studies support square-pyramidal geometry for the vanadium(IV) complexes.

Isatin (1) also known as indole-2,3-dione, can be considered to be the *o*-quinone of 2,3-dihydroxyindole. It is a unique molecule possessing both amide and ketocarbonyl groups. Apart from this, it has an active hydrogen atom attached to nitrogen (or oxygen) and an aromatic ring which should substitute at 5- and 7-positions. It exists in a tautomeric form (2) and these functional characteristics play an important role in governing the various reactions of the molecule¹.

(1)

(2)

The C-3 carbonyl group of isatin is strongly electrophilic. As a result, isatin is readily involved in condensation and addition reactions. However, the coordination behaviour of hydrazones derived from isatin is practically unknown. Hassaan *et al.* reported nickel(II) chelates of Schiff bases derived from isatin with amino acids and substituted hydrazines². The acid amide group present in hydrazones is known to play a significant role in many biological processes. On the other hand, metal binding properties of acid amides are of special relevance to the chemistry of proteins, which contain a number of amide linkage in their structures. The coordination behaviour of hydrazones is well studied which depend upon pH of the medium, nature of substituent and position of hydrazone group relative to other nucleus^{3,4}.

In this paper, we report the preparation and characterization of oxovanadium(IV) complexes with isatin hydrazones.

Results and discussion

The condensation reactions of isatin with aromatic acid hydrazides in ethanol give rise to hydrazone ligands (3) as shown below :

A systematic study of reactions of oxovanadium(IV) sulphate with isatin hydrazones have been studied in methanol in 1 : 1 molar ratio and in the presence of 30% NaOH. The complexes of type $[VO(L)H_2O]$ are obtained according to the following reaction :

where, $LH_2 = IPH_2, ICH_2, INH_2$ and IMH_2

Elemental analyses of the complexes are given in Table 1. The resulting complexes are brown to greenish brown coloured solids; soluble in tetrahydrofuran, dimethylformamide and dimethylsulphoxide. Conductance measurements in dimethylformamide reveal that the complexes are non-electrolytes. The presence of water molecule in the complexes is inferred from thermogravimetric studies which show weight loss at 160–175°C corresponding to one water molecule.

Table 1. Reactions of oxovanadium(IV) sulphate with isatin hydrazones

Reactants	Molar ratio	Refluxing time (h)	Product, colour, yield (%)	Analysis : Found (Calcd.) %			
				C	H	N	V
VOSO ₄ .5H ₂ O + IPH ₂	1 : 1	14	[VO(IP)H ₂ O], Greenish brown, 60	51.6 (51.7)	3.1 (3.2)	11.9 (12.1)	14.6 (14.6)
VOSO ₄ .5H ₂ O + ICH ₂	1 : 1	16	[VO(IC)H ₂ O], Brown, 64	47.0 (47.1)	2.6 (2.6)	10.8 (11.0)	13.2 (13.3)
VOSO ₄ .5H ₂ O + INH ₂	1 : 1	14	[VO(IN)H ₂ O], Dark brown, 70	45.6 (45.8)	2.5 (2.6)	14.0 (14.2)	12.9 (13.0)
VOSO ₄ .5H ₂ O + IMH ₂	1 : 1	16	[VO(IM)H ₂ O], Dark brown, 55	52.7 (53.0)	3.4 (3.6)	11.4 (11.6)	13.9 (14.0)

where, IPH₂ = Hydrazone derived from isatin and benzoic acid hydrazide, ICH₂ = hydrazone derived from isatin and 4-chlorobenzoic acid hydrazide, INH₂ = hydrazone derived from isatin and 4-nitrobenzoic acid hydrazide and IMH₂ = hydrazone derived from isatin and 4-methoxybenzoic acid hydrazide.

Magnetic moment and electronic spectra :

The magnetic moments of the oxovanadium(IV) complexes lie in the range 1.70–1.78 B.M. at room temperature. These values are well within the range reported⁵ for monomeric oxovanadium(IV) complexes. In the electronic spectra, three bands are observed in the regions 10750–12200, 15500–16000 and 21000–22500 cm⁻¹ (Table 2). These bands are nearly the same as reported^{6,7} for other five-coordinated oxovanadium(IV) complexes. Several schemes have been advanced to interpret the electronic spectra of oxovanadium(IV) complexes^{8–10}. Three-band spectrum has been predicated for five-coordinate complexes possessing the effective C_{4v} symmetry of a square pyramid. Ballhausen and Gray proposed¹¹, the energy level scheme for [VO(H₂O)₅]²⁺. In this model, the unpaired electron resides in a largely non bonding d_{xy} orbital (z-axis is taken as the vanadyl bond) with lobes pointing between the equatorial ligands. The interaction of d_{xz}, d_{yz} with the ligand may be π-acceptor in character and the relative order of the B₂ and E orbitals could be inverted. Usually, three optical bands are observed for visible;

- (1) ${}^2B_2 (d_{xy}) \rightarrow {}^2E (d_{xz}, d_{yz})$
- (2) ${}^2B_2 (d_{xy}) \rightarrow {}^2B_1 (d_{x^2-y^2})$
- (3) ${}^2B_2 (d_{xy}) \rightarrow {}^2A_1 (d_{z^2})$

Table 2. Magnetic moments and electronic spectral bands of oxovanadium complexes with isatin hydrazones

Complex	μ _B (300 K)	Electronic spectral bands (cm ⁻¹)		
		${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$	${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$	${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$
[VO(IP)H ₂ O]	1.75	10750	15800	21800
[VO(IC)H ₂ O]	1.78	11800	15500	22500
[VO(IN)H ₂ O]	1.70	12200	16000	22000
[VO(IM)H ₂ O]	1.72	11500	15600	22200

For some complexes, four bands are observed, possibly arising from the splitting of d_{xz}, d_{yz} levels in low symmetry.

Accordingly, the observed bands can be assigned to $b_2 \rightarrow e\pi^* ({}^2B_2 \rightarrow E)$, $b_2 \rightarrow b_1^* ({}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1)$ and $b_2 \rightarrow a_1^* ({}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1)$ transitions in increasing order of energy. The second transition corresponds to 10 Dq. One more band is observed at ca. 32000–35000 cm⁻¹, which may be due to intra-ligand transition.

Infrared spectra :

The bonding sites of hydrazones involved in the oxovanadium(IV) complexes have been determined by careful comparison of the infrared spectra of the complexes with the spectra of ligands. The important features of the spectra are summarized below :

Amino and amido groups vibrations : The IR spectra of ligands show band at ca. 3200–3120 cm⁻¹ which may be due to ν(N–H) vibration¹². All the ligands show bands in the 1650–1640 cm⁻¹, 1540–1520 cm⁻¹ and 1300 cm⁻¹ regions assignable^{3,4} to amide-I [ν(C=O)], amide-II [ν(C–N) + δ(N–H)] and amide-III [δ(N–H)] vibrations, respectively. These bands disappear in the complexes suggesting enolization of the keto group by the forming of complexes through deprotonation.

The presence of strong characteristic bands for ν(C=N) and ν(N=CO) in the 1570–1560 cm⁻¹ and 1520–1510 cm⁻¹ regions, respectively, further support³ enolization of the keto group. The coordination through enolic oxygen through deprotonation is further confirmed by the appearance of band at ca. 470–480 cm⁻¹ assignable⁷ to ν(V–O) vibration.

The spectra of the ligands also show two bands at ca. 3280 cm⁻¹ and 1700 cm⁻¹ assignable^{13,14} to ν(N–H) and ν(C=O) vibrations of the isatin ring. In the spectra of oxovanadium(IV) complexes both these bands disappear suggesting enolization of keto group. These complexes show

one strong band at *ca.* 1585 cm^{-1} due to newly formed $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$.

Table 3. ESR parameters of oxovanadium(IV) complexes with isatin hydrazones

Complexes	g_{av}	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	A_{av}	A_{\parallel}	A_{\perp}
[VO(IP)H ₂ O]	1.979	1.952	1.991	87	161	50
[VO(IC)H ₂ O]	1.974	1.950	1.986	88	161	52
[VO(IN)H ₂ O]	1.969	1.948	1.979	87	160	50
[VO(IM)H ₂ O]	1.972	1.950	1.980	90	165	52

Azomethine group vibration : The infrared spectra of isatin hydrazones show band at *ca.* 1630–1620 cm^{-1} which can be assigned⁶ to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ of the azomethine linkage. In the complexes, this band appears at slightly lower wave number (20–25 cm^{-1} , at 1600 cm^{-1}) suggesting that the nitrogen atom of the azomethine group is coordinated to metal atom. The $\nu(\text{V}-\text{N})$ vibration^{7,15} appears at *ca.* 360–340 cm^{-1} .

V=O group vibrations : The spectra of all oxovanadium(IV) complexes show a new characteristic band around 970–975 cm^{-1} which are assigned¹⁶ to $\nu(\text{V}=\text{O})$ vibration.

In addition, all the complexes show a strong band at *ca.* 3350 cm^{-1} , assignable to $\nu(\text{OH})$ of coordinated water molecule. Thus, the IR spectral studies indicate that the isatin hydrazone ligands, in basic medium, behaves as dibasic, tridentate chelating agent having coordination sites at two enolic oxygen atoms and the azomethine nitrogen atom.

Electron spin resonance spectra :

⁵¹V is in 99.8% natural abundance and has a nuclear spin $I = 7/2$. In fluid solution, eight hyperfine lines are observed exhibiting a variation in line width. Hyperfine coupling are large (~100 gauss), but a large nuclear moment and spin cause a large line width which tends to obscure s.h.f.s. Almost all vanadium compounds have symmetry less than Oh and Td, and so ESR signals are readily observed because of the longer relaxation time¹⁷. At room temperature, there is free rotation of the vanadyl group, as manifest by the isotropic spectrum. At lower temperature the spectrum becomes anisotropic. ESR studies on the large number of vanadyl complexes, shows that most VO²⁺ complexes have the square-pyramidal structure and may frequently add on Lewis bases to the sixth coordination position.

Kuska and Roger¹⁸ and Guzy, Raynor, and Symons¹⁹ have measured g and A_{iso} (⁵¹V) for vanadyl acetylacetonate in numerous solvents and bases. There is a trend to lower A_{iso} values with increase in basicity (because of greater delocalization of the unpaired electron), and the systems are very sensitive to solvation and coordination. Walker *et al.*²⁰ and

Kuska and Roger¹⁸ compared the spectra of VO(acac)₂ with that of vanadyl trifluoroacetoacetate and hexafluoroacetoacetate and observed h.f.s. of 108.19, 110.09 and 112.6 gauss, respectively. The higher A_{iso} (⁵¹V) value is associated with greater localization of the electron on the metal because of the increased electrophilic nature of the ligands and consequent reduced covalency of the V–O (chelate) bonds. Solutions of VOCl₂ in water, acetone, dilute HCl and concentrated HCl have A_{iso} values of 117, 110, 115.9 and 110.9 gauss, respectively, showing how the basicity of the primary solvation sphere affects the hyperfine coupling to vanadium. Several mixed chelates, which, have two oxygen and two nitrogen bonding atoms, have been studied^{21,22}. Their ESR parameters are, in general, like those of VO(acac)₂.

Vanadyl phthalocyanine²³ and substituted vanadyl porphyrins²⁴ have been extensively studied. It was observed that the ¹⁴N s.h.f. tensor is almost isotropic which indicates that the unpaired electron in the b_{2g}^* orbital is localized mainly on the metal and that in-plane π -bonding is slight.

Fig. 1. ESR spectra of [VO(IP)H₂O] in DMSO at (a) room temperature and (b) liquid nitrogen temperature.

Splitting of the vanadium perpendicular features into A_x and A_y has only been seen in a few cases and arises from the asymmetry of the chelating ligand. In all cases $g_{\parallel} < g_{\perp} < 2$ which is in agreement with prediction.

The X-band EPR spectra of oxovanadium(IV) complexes were recorded at room temperature and at liquid nitrogen temperature (Fig. 1). The polycrystalline sample data show significant temperature dependence. At ambient temperature, intense EPR spectra are observed. These spectra display typical eight line pattern of vanadium (^{51}V ; $I = 7/2$) with isotropic g_0 values and hyperfine coupling parameters A_0 given in Table 3. The g average values determined from the spectra are *ca.* 1.98, similar to the spin-only values (free electron value) of 2.00 suggesting little spin orbital coupling. At the liquid nitrogen temperature, the spectra display well resolved axial anisotropy with two sets of eight-line pattern. The g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp} , A_{\parallel} and A_{\perp} values are given in Table 3. The values are typical of the spectra displayed by square pyramidal oxovanadium(IV) complexes with unpaired electron in an orbital of mostly d_{xy} character. Inspection of these data reveals a close agreement between the spectral parameters obtained at room temperature and at liquid nitrogen temperature; [$g_{\text{iv}} = 1/3 (g_{\parallel} + 2g_{\perp})$; $A_{\text{iv}} = 1/3 (A_{\parallel} + 2A_{\perp})$], thus indicating the complexes retain their structural identity throughout this temperature range.

Thus, on the basis of above studies, the following structure (4) may be tentatively proposed for oxovanadium(IV) complexes :

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. All solvents used were distilled before use. The ligands were prepared by the condensation of isatin with appropriate hydrazide as reported in the literature¹³. The details of analytical methods and physical measurements were the same as described earlier⁷.

Preparation of complexes :

Oxovanadium(IV) sulphate (0.01 mol) dissolved in methanol (15 cm³) was added to a refluxing solution of

hydrazone (0.01 mol) in methanol (20 cm³) containing saturated alcoholic solution of sodium hydroxide (5 cm³). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 14–16 h. Coloured precipitate, so obtained was filtered, washed thoroughly with methanol and dried under vacuo. Yield 60%.

The details of the reactions and physical characteristics of the products formed are listed in Table 1. The analytical data of the products are given in Table 1.

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